

0.989**) between SPAD-501 reading and chlorophyll content (see figure). The instrument manufacturer obtained a correlation of 0.815 between chlorophyll reading and actual chlorophyll content

using data from several crop species. SPAD-501 is reliable in determining relative chlorophyll content as an index of cold tolerance.

This method has considerable

potential in quantifying leaf discoloration due to low temperature as well as yellowing caused by other stresses such as nutrient deficiency, diseases, and drought. *J*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Response of rice varieties to protective irrigation

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Extended breaks in monsoon rainfall significantly reduce yield of rice grown on lateritic soils with high infiltration, medium to high total N, high K, and low P in Konkan, India. Yield losses are greatest on newly developed, terraced uplands. Protective irrigation may reduce those losses.

We evaluated 135-d Jaya and RP4-14 for response to protective irrigation in a factorial randomized block design with 5 replications on newly developed terraces of lateritic soil. Rice was sown 9 Jun 1984 and transplanted on 5 Sep at 3 seedlings/hill and 20- × 15-cm spacing. Plots received 50-22-41.5 kg NPK/ha at transplanting and 50 kg N in 2 equal splits at 1-mo intervals. Plots received 251.84 mm of water at each protective

Influence of protective irrigation on grain and straw yield, Maharashtra, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)			
	Control		Protective irrigation	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
Jaya	2.9	3.1	3.9	4.1
RP4-14	3.1	3.1	3.9	4.0
Mean	3.0	3.4	3.9	4.0
		S. Em. ±	CD at 5%	
Variety:	Grain	0.1	ns	
	Straw	0.1	ns	
Irrigation:	Grain	0.1	0.4	
	Straw	0.1	0.3	
Interaction:	Grain	0.2	ns	
	Straw	0.1	0.4	

irrigation (13 Jul; 19, 21, 24, and 27 Sep; and 1 Oct). Recommended pest control measures were applied. Harvest was 25 Oct.

Yields were relatively low. Protective irrigation increased yield an average 30% over that of the control (see table). *J*

IET7613, a drought-resistant upland rice

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Improved short-duration, drought-

resistant, upland varieties are needed for the Uttar Pradesh plains, where rainy season seldom lasts more than 90 d. Newly developed IET7613 (M63-83/Cauvery) yields 15% more at low to moderate soil fertility than locally grown N22. IET7613 is a semidwarf, drought-resistant upland rice that matures in 85 d.

Rainfall distribution in Faizabad, India, during upland trials in 1982-84.